

An Overview of Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy: Implications for Guidance and Counselling

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Abstract

This paper overviewed conceptual framework on rational emotive behaviour therapy such as originator of REBT, history of Albert Ellis, his philosophical viewpoint of Albert Ellis REBT, determinant factors of personality by Albert Ellis REBT, Rational Emotive Behaviour Theory of Psychotherapy, Goal of REBT, Assessment, the therapeutic approaches, the A-B-C-D-E therapeutic approaches, other cognitive approaches, emotive techniques, behaviour methods and implications for guidance and counselling programmes in Nigerian within and outside school setting. It was recommended that seminars and workshops should constantly be organized for guidance and counselling officers/teachers to improve on their knowledge and skills on effective application of REBT techniques within and outside school setting.

Key words: Overview, Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy, Implications, Guidance, Counselling

Introduction

Albert Ellis originated an approach that he believed would be more effective and efficient in bringing about psychotherapeutic change. His approach is primarily a cognitive one, although it has significant behavioural and emotive aspects. Essential to his theory is his A-B-C model, which is applied to understanding personality and to effecting personality change. This model holds that individuals respond to an activating event (A) with emotional and behavioural consequences (C). The emotional and behavioural consequences are not only caused by the activating event (A), but partly by the individual's belief system (B). When the activating event (A) is a pleasant one, the resulting beliefs are likely to be innocuous. However, when the activating events are not pleasant, irrational beliefs may develop. These irrational beliefs (B) often cause difficult emotional and behavioural consequences (C). A major role of the therapist is to dispute (D) these irrational beliefs (B) by challenging them through a variety of disputation techniques. Also, a number of other cognitive, emotive, and behavioral techniques are used to bring about therapeutic change. Although this outline of REBT is relatively simple, the practice of REBT is not. Assessing, disputing, and changing irrational beliefs require familiarity with

assessment of implicit irrational beliefs and knowledge of a wide variety of cognitive, emotive, and behavioural techniques for individuals, families, and groups (Sharf, 2012).

History of Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy

Albert Ellis, the founder and developer of REBT, was born in Pittsburgh in 1913 and moved to New York City 4 years later. He grew up in New York, did all his schooling there, founded a training institute there, the Institute for Rational Living (later the Albert Ellis Institute) in 1959, and lived and worked there until his death in 2007 at the age of 93. During his childhood, Albert, the oldest of three children, was often sick and was hospitalized nine times, mainly for problems related to kidney disease. As a result, Ellis developed a pattern of taking care of himself and being self-responsible. Making his breakfast and lunch and getting to school by himself are early indicators of the self-sufficiency that was to be a trademark of Ellis's approach to education and professional life. His father, businessman, was often away from home, and Ellis described his mother as neglectful of her family. In looking back at his childhood, Ellis stated: "I invented rational emotive behavior therapy naturally, beginning even back then, because it was my tendency" (Sharf, 2010). But during his adolescence, Ellis was quite shy with girls. Using a method that foreshadows REBT, he made himself talk to 100 girls at the Bronx Botanical Gardens during a 1-month period. Although he was not successful in getting a date, this method helped Ellis decrease his fear of rejection. Also shy about speaking in front of groups, Ellis used a similar approach to overcome this fear, so much so that he later came to enjoy public speaking. Ellis received his undergraduate degree at the City College of New York in 1934. Between graduation from college and entering graduate school at the age of 28, he wrote novels and worked as a personnel manager in a small business. After obtaining his Ph.D. in 1947 at Columbia University, he started work at a New Jersey mental hygiene clinic while receiving analysis from Richard Hulbeck, a psychiatrist, who was later to supervise Ellis in his early psychoanalytic work. ALBERT ELLIS in the 1940s Ellis published several articles on personality assessment questionnaires. Having been interested in philosophy since the age of 16, Ellis returned to philosophy to determine ways to help individuals change their philosophical point of view and combat self-defeating behaviour (Ellis, 2005). In 1956, at the American Psychological Association annual convention, Ellis gave his first paper on rational therapy. He later regretted using the term *rational therapy*, because many psychologists misinterpreted it as meaning therapy without emotion. That was not Ellis's intention, and he spent time trying to clarify and explain his position. Although other psychologists were developing other direct methods of dealing with clients at about the same time, none made such consistent and pronounced efforts in explicating their point of view as did Ellis. Although Ellis was an adjunct professor of psychology at three universities, he devoted his energy to his practice of individual and group REBT and the training of therapists at the Albert Ellis Institute in New York. Established in 1959, the nonprofit institute provides workshops, therapist training and individual and group psychotherapy. Ellis also initiated the *Journal of Rational-Emotive Behaviour and Cognitive-Behaviour Therapy*. Ellis's theory of personality is based not only on psychological, biological, and sociological data but also on philosophy. His philosophical approach features responsible hedonism and humanism, which,

combined with a belief in rationality, influenced his personality theory (Dobson & Dozois, 2010). Ellis was interested in biological, social, and psychological factors that make individuals vulnerable to psychological disturbances that are cognitive, behavioural, and emotional in nature. It is particularly the cognitive factors that Ellis emphasizes, attending to the irrational beliefs that help create disturbances in individuals' lives (Sharf, 2012).

Philosophical Viewpoints

Ellis was interested particularly in the Stoic philosophers and was influenced by Epictetus, a Roman philosopher who said, "People are disturbed not by things, but by their view of things" (Sharf, 2010). He was also affected by European philosophers who dealt with the issues of happiness and rationality, such as Baruch Spinoza, Friedrich Nietzsche, and Immanuel Kant, as well as Arthur Schopenhauer's concept of "the world as will and idea" (Sharf, 2010). The writings of more modern philosophers, including John Dewey, Bertrand Russell, and Karl Popper (a philosopher of science), influenced Ellis to emphasize cognition in his development of REBT (DiGiuseppe, 2010) the philosophical underpinnings of REBT include responsible hedonism, humanism, and rationality.

Responsible hedonism

Although hedonism refers to the concept of seeking pleasure and avoiding pain, responsible hedonism concerns maintaining pleasure over the long term by avoiding short-term pleasures that lead to pain, such as drug abuse and alcohol addiction. Ellis believes that people are often extremely hedonistic but need to focus on long-range rather than short-range hedonism (Dryden & Ellis, 2003). Although REBT does not tell people what to enjoy, its practitioners believe that enjoyment is a major goal in life. This point of view does not lead to irresponsible behaviour because individuals with a responsible attitude toward hedonism think through the consequences of their behaviour on others as well as on themselves. Manipulating and exploiting others is not in the long-range interest of individuals. An example of Ellis's attention to hedonism is his work directed at irrational beliefs that people have regarding sexuality that interfere with their experience of sexual pleasure. His many books on the subject are a way of promoting responsible hedonism (Sharf, 2010).

Humanism

Practitioners of REBT view human beings as holistic, goal-directed organisms who are important because they are alive. This position is consistent with that of ethical humanism, which emphasizes human interests over the interests of a deity, leading to misinterpretations that Ellis is against religion. He has stated, "It is not religion, but religiosity, that is a cause of psychopathology. Religiosity is an absolutistic faith that is not based on fact" (Ellis, 2001). Ellis (2001) believes that accepting absolute notions of right and wrong, and of damnation if one acts wrongly, without thinking them through leads to guilt, anxiety, depression, and other psychological dysfunctions.

Rationality

Rationality refers to people using efficient, flexible, logical, and scientific ways of attempting to achieve their values and goals (Wilson, 2010), not to the absence of feelings or emotions. Therapy with REBT shows individuals how they can get more of what they want from life by being rational (efficient, logical, and flexible). This means that they may reexamine early parental or religious teachings or beliefs they had previously accepted. As this is done, they develop a new philosophy of life that leads to increased long-range happiness (responsible hedonism). These philosophies, which have been abbreviated here, are communicated to clients to help them not only alleviate current problems but also develop a philosophy of life that will help them deal with problems as they present themselves.

Ellis Outline Factors Basic to the Rational Emotive Behaviour Theory of Personality

Ellis has recognized a number of factors that contribute to an individual's personality development and personality disturbances, including strong biological and social aspects that present a challenge to the therapist to help change. Depending on biological and social factors, individuals are varyingly vulnerable to emotional disturbance.

Biological factors

Impressed by the power of biological factors in determining human personality, Ellis has said, "I am still haunted by the reality, however, that humans ... have a strong biological tendency to needlessly and severely disturb themselves, and that, to make matters much worse, they also are powerfully predisposed to unconsciously and habitually prolong their mental dysfunctioning and to fight like hell against giving it up" (Ellis, 1987). Writing that individuals have powerful innate tendencies to hurt themselves or to think in irrational ways, He believes that individuals have inborn tendencies to react to events in certain patterns, regardless of environmental factors that may affect events, by damning themselves and others when they do not get what they want. Additionally, he also believes that certain severe mental disturbances are partly inherited and have strong biological components. For example, schizophrenia is illustrative of biological limitations that inhibit thinking clearly and logically.

Social factors

Interpersonal relationships in families, peer groups, schools, and other social groups have an impact on the expectations that individuals have of themselves and others (Ellis, 2003). They are likely to define themselves as good or worthwhile, depending on how they see others reacting to them. If they feel accepted by others, they are likely to feel good about themselves. Individuals receiving criticism from parents, teachers, or peers are likely to view themselves as bad or worthless or in other negative ways. From a rational emotive behavior perspective, individuals who feel worthless or bad about themselves are often caring too much about the views and values of others. According to Ellis, social institutions such as schools and religions are likely to promote absolutist values that suggest the proper ways of relating to others in terms of manners, customs, sexuality, and family relationships (Ellis, 2001). Individuals often are faced with dealing with the

“musts” and “shoulds” they have incorporated from their interactions with others. For example, if an individual believes she absolutely must pray twice a day, that belief has been partly learned through religious training. Ellis does not say that this value of praying is inappropriate; rather, he encourages individuals to question their absolutist “musts” and “shoulds.”

Vulnerability to disturbance

Depending on social and biological factors, individuals vary as to how vulnerable they are to psychological disturbance. They often have goals to enjoy themselves when alone or in social groups, to enjoy an intimate sexual relationship with another, to enjoy productive work, and to enjoy a variety of recreational activities (Dryden & Ellis, 2001, 2003). Opposing these desires are dysfunctional beliefs that thwart their ability to meet or enjoy these goals.

The Rational Emotive Behavior A-B-C Theory of Personality

The focus of rational emotive behaviour personality theory is the A-B-C model of personality. Individuals have goals that may be supported or thwarted by activating events (As). They then react, consciously or unconsciously, with their belief system (B), by which they respond to the activating event with something such as, “This is nice.” They also experience the emotional or behavioural consequence of the activating event. This system works well for individuals when the activating events are pleasant and support their goals. When the activating events no longer support their goals, there is potential for disturbance in this system. The potential exists for the belief system to be irrational or dysfunctional, which can lead to further disturbances. When individuals believe something must happen as they wish, emotional disturbance occurs. This is particularly true when tolerance for frustration is low (Leahy, 2017). Although these concepts appear simple, they can, when fully developed, become quite complex (Dryden, DiGiuseppe & Neenan, 2003; Dryden & Ellis, 2003). To illustrate these principles, here is Kelly, who has a goal to become a psychologist and a sub-goal to do well on her psychology examination.

Rational belief: pleasant activating event

The A-B-C theory of personality functions well and, for most people, goes unnoticed when the activating events are pleasant. When Kelly receives an A on her psychology exam (activating event), her belief (B) in her ability to do well on the psychology exam and to become a psychologist is supported. The consequence is an emotional experience of pleasure and a behavioural anticipation of the next psychology examination, an activating event.

Rational belief: unpleasant activating event

When the activating event is unpleasant, many different beliefs and consequences can result. If Kelly fails her psychology exam, the activating event (A), she may experience a belief (B) such as “This is too bad; I don’t like to fail a test.” She may experience a healthy emotional consequence of feeling frustrated by her performance on the test. She may also choose to study hard for the next test (an upcoming activating event) so that she will not experience this behavioural consequence again.

Irrational belief: unpleasant activating event

When individuals do not experience activating events in a way that is congruent with their belief systems (B), they may react with irrational beliefs (IBs). Rather than saying, "It is unfortunate, it is too bad," they may say, "I ought to have, I should, I must, I have to, have my goals fulfilled." Furthermore, they may say, "If my goals are not fulfilled, it is awful," "I can't stand it," "I'm a terrible person," and so forth. It is these irrational beliefs that contribute to emotional disturbance. They are usually followed by emotional consequences such as "I feel depressed and hopeless" or "I am extremely angry." Behavioural consequences may be avoidance, attack, or a whole range of inappropriate reactions. When Kelly fails her psychology exam (A, an activating event), she may react by believing, "I have to have an A on the exam" or "I am a worthless person because I didn't get an A." She may experience an unhealthy emotional consequence, such as deep despair, a sense of worthlessness, and a choice not to study for other courses—a behavioural consequence.

Disturbances about disturbances

Ellis believes that individuals largely upset themselves through their belief systems. They can become disturbed about the consequences resulting from an unfortunate activating event. People may disturb themselves by turning a disturbed consequence into a new activating event. Kelly may continue by saying, "I feel depressed and worthless!"—a new activating event. The new belief that follows is "That is really awful!" This leaves her with a new consequence in which her feelings of worthlessness and upset are even greater. This new upset (new C) can become a third activating event, such as "I am the most worthless person in the world," and the cycle can continue ad infinitum. Thus, Kelly was depressed about her examination performance but became depressed and upset about being depressed. She criticized herself for doing poorly on the exam, felt depressed because she criticized herself, then criticized herself for being overly critical, and then criticized herself for not seeing that she is being critical, and then for not stopping being critical. She can further say, "I am more critical than others, and I'm more depressed than others, and nothing can be done about how hopeless I am." In such a way, individuals can be overwhelmed by their irrational belief systems (Sharf, 2012).

Interrelationship between A, B, and C

Although the A-B-C personality theory may appear rather simple, Ellis has explained the variety of interactions among A, B, and C. Activating events, beliefs, and consequences can each have components that are emotional, behavioural, or cognitive. Furthermore, each of these (A, B, and C) can influence and interact with each other. Ellis and his colleagues (Browne, Dowd & Freeman, 2010) describe how cognition, emotions, and behaviours affect one another and combine into a set of dysfunctional philosophical assumptions leading to emotional disturbance. "**Musts**" Implicit in individuals' consequences are musts, such as "I must do well on the exam," "I must get an A in the course," "I must become a psychologist," and so forth. Ellis (2008) states that musts not only are intellectual and cognitive but also have elements that are highly emotional

and others that is behavioural. Musts are a part of goals, activating events, beliefs, and ineffective consequences.

Ellis (1962) lists 12 musts that he believes are common to many individuals, examples of which follow:

I must be loved by everyone I know.

I must be competent, adequate, and achieving in all respects to be worthwhile.

Some people are wicked and must be severely blamed and punished for what they have done.

It is awful when things don't go the way I want them to.

Things must go the way I want them to.

I must worry about dangerous things that I cannot control.

I must rely on someone stronger than myself.

I must become worried about other people's problems.

I must find the right solution to my problems.

Ellis (1962) divides these irrational beliefs into three categories: demands about self, demands about others, and demands about the world and/or life conditions. Ellis has developed the term *musturbation* for all types of must statements. Musturbating develops irrational beliefs and leads to emotional disturbance. For Kelly to say, "I must get an A on my exam, or I will be a worthless person, and no one will ever respect me" is an example of an irrational belief that can lead to her becoming anxious, fearful, panicky about exams, and physically tense.

Low frustration tolerance

Individuals who cannot tolerate frustration easily are more likely to be disturbed than those who can (Leahy, 2017). Such statements as "That's too difficult," "I can't take the pressure," and "I'm too frightened to do it" are examples of low frustration tolerance. A personal philosophy maintaining that one should not have to do anything unpleasant or uncomfortable can lead to frustration in obtaining goals. If Kelly is frustrated easily by her poor performance on one exam, she may give up on her goal of becoming a psychologist and develop anxiety, depression, and so forth.

Anxiety

Related to the concept of low frustration tolerance to disturbance is anxiety. Ellis (2008) describes two types of anxiety—discomfort anxiety and ego anxiety. In discomfort anxiety, individuals' comfort level is threatened and they must get what they want (low frustration tolerance). In ego anxiety, individuals' sense of self-worth is threatened and they feel that they must perform well. In discomfort and ego anxiety, individuals have a belief that if they don't get or do what they want, the results will be awful or catastrophic. Kelly may experience discomfort anxiety if she does not get an A, which she badly wants, on her exam. She may feel ego anxiety if she does not get an A because her sense of worth may be threatened. The A-B-C theory of personality is also the central focus for personality change.

Rational Emotive Behaviour Theory of Psychotherapy

A characteristic of REBT is its combination of philosophical change with cognitive, behavioural, and emotive strategies to bring about both short-range and long-range change. The emphasis on cognition has its antecedents in Adlerian psychotherapy, which has a strong focus on individuals' beliefs. The goals of REBT stress the use and adoption of the A-B-C theory of personality. Although assessment instruments are used, the A-B-C theory is the core of assessment as well as of psychotherapy. Rational emotive behaviour therapists vary their approach to the development of the relationship with a client, but all acknowledge the importance of acceptance of the client as an individual. The core approach to REBT is to dispute irrational thoughts; however, many other cognitive, emotive, and behavioural approaches are used to bring about change and meet clients' goals.

Goals of Therapy

The general goals of REBT are to assist people in minimizing emotional disturbances, decreasing self-defeating self behaviours (irrational ideas), and becoming more self-actualized so that they can lead a happier existence (rational ideas) (Ellis, 2005). Major sub-goals are to help individuals think more clearly and rationally, feel more appropriately, and act more efficiently and effectively in achieving goals of living happily. Individuals learn to deal effectively with negative feelings such as sorrow, regret, frustration, and annoyance. They deal with unhealthy negative feelings such as depression, anxiety, and worthlessness by using an effective rational emotive behaviour philosophy.

For Ellis (2008), the philosophy of REBT distinguishes it from other cognitive therapies and makes it more efficient and elegant. Although REBT helps individuals minimize or remove emotional disturbances, it is the teaching of philosophical change that prevents individuals from re-disturbing themselves with overwhelming irrational thoughts. The A-B-C philosophy can help clients see when they are creating new symptoms or re-creating previous ones. The global goals of REBT can be applied to specific client goals through the use of A-B-C personality theory (DiGiuseppe, 2010).

Assessment

REBT assessment is of two overlapping types. The first is assessment of cognition and behaviours that are sources for the problems, as well as themes of cognition, emotions, and behaviours. The second is the use of the A-B-C theory of personality to identify client problems. Both of these methods, but especially the latter, continue throughout the therapeutic process. This assessment is driven by hypotheses that therapists make as they listen to their clients. In addition to therapy-oriented assessment, a wide variety of scales and tests can be used to assess client concerns (Macavei & McMahan, 2010).

The A-B-C assessment usually starts from the beginning of the first session and continues throughout therapy. Therapists listen while clients describe feelings and behaviours (consequences) that they feel are caused by specific experiences (activating events). As the client describes problems, therapists listen to the beliefs the clients have about the activating event.

Therapists differ as to how long they will listen to descriptions of emotional and behavioural problems before determining irrational beliefs. As the therapeutic process continues, therapists may revise or hear new irrational beliefs (Macavei & McMahon, 2010).

The Therapeutic Relationship

The process of assessment and the development of a therapeutic relationship are often closely related in REBT. Ellis believed that the best way to develop a therapeutic relationship is to help solve the client's immediate problem (Ellis, 2001). After asking the client what he wishes to discuss, Ellis then identifies the activating events, irrational beliefs, and emotional and behavioural consequences. He may do this for two or three sessions and then possibly work on larger, or other, issues. Clients see and hear that they are being listened to and responded to. Ellis suggests that this is a type of advanced empathy in which the therapist understands the basic philosophies that underlie client communications. Clients not only feel understood but also sense that therapists understand their feelings better than they do.

The A-B-C-D-E Therapeutic Approach

The core of REBT is the application of the A-B-C philosophy to client problems. Often this approach is used in the first and subsequent sessions. Where possible, therapists prefer to explain and make explicit each of the three aspects. In addition, therapeutic interventions require the use of D and E. There are three basic types of disputation (D): detecting irrational beliefs, discriminating irrational from rational beliefs, and debating irrational beliefs. When beliefs have been actively and successfully disputed, clients will experience E, a new effect—a logical philosophy and a new level of affect appropriate to the problem. In working with the A-B-C-D-E model, therapists can experience issues and difficulties in application to their clients.

A (activating event): the activating event can be divided into two parts: what happened and what the client perceived happened. Often it is helpful to ask for specifics to confirm an activating event. For example, the activating event “dead of husband” combines an event with a perception and an evaluation. To ascertain the activating event, the therapist might ask, “What was your social, emotional and psychological relationship with your husband at that point?” Getting a clear and active picture of the activating event, while avoiding unnecessary detail and vagueness, is quite helpful. Occasionally, clients present too many activating events, and therapists need to focus on only a few. Therapists also need to be alert as to when a previous consequence becomes an activating event. Sometimes it is possible to change an activating event, such as avoiding a possible confrontation, but doing so may not help clients deal with their irrational behaviour or make more than temporary changes.

C (consequences): Clients often start the first therapy session with their consequences—“I feel very depressed.” Sometimes inexperienced therapists can have difficulty in discriminating between beliefs and consequences. One difference is that feelings cannot be disputed—they are experiences—whereas beliefs can be disputed. When dealing with feelings, clients may be unclear about their emotions, mislabel them, or exaggerate them. Often, but not always, consequences can be changed by altering beliefs. However, clients must be willing for those consequences to

occur. For example, if a widow wishes to feel better about herself in her thinking, she should be willing to change angry feelings (irrational thinking) about her situation that are debilitating.

B (beliefs): As discussed earlier, there are two types of beliefs—rational and irrational. Irrational beliefs are exaggerated and absolutistic, lead to disturbed feelings, and do not help individuals attain their goals. Rational beliefs generate adaptive and healthy emotions and behaviours (David, Freeman & DiGiuseppe, 2010). Being familiar with typical irrational beliefs (Ellis, 2003) can be helpful in learning to identify beliefs so that they can be disputed.

D (disputing): A common and important approach in REBT is to teach the A-B-C philosophy to clients and then to dispute irrational beliefs (Ellis, 2003). Disputing has three parts: detecting, discriminating, and debating irrational beliefs. The therapist first detects irrational beliefs in the client and helps the client detect irrational beliefs in his perceptions. Irrational beliefs may underlie several activating events; for example, a widow may experience stress on the death of her husband because she feels that everyone is accusing her for the death of her husband so everybody in the family is against her. Detecting the irrational belief “Others must find me innocent and witty” is the first part of disputing.

Discriminating irrational from rational beliefs is the next step. Being aware of *musts*, *shoulds*, *oughts*, and other unrealistic demands helps the client learn which beliefs are rational and which are not. A major emphasis in REBT is debating irrational beliefs. The therapist questions the client: “Why must everybody like you in the family of your late husband?” “Why must you be sympathized by everybody in the family of your deceased husband?” Debating irrational beliefs helps clients change their beliefs to rational ones, which diminishes their emotional discomfort. Several strategies of disputing or debating irrational beliefs can be used: the lecture, the Socratic debate, humor, creativity, and self-disclosure (Sharf, 2010). Using the lecture approach (or, better, mini-lecture), the therapist gives the client an explanation of why her irrational belief is self-defeating. Obtaining feedback from the client that she understands what has been explained is important. A simple “yes” or “no” from the client is insufficient. In the Socratic style, the therapist points out the lack of logic and the inconsistencies in the client’s belief, encouraging argument from the client, so that the client does not just accept the therapist’s point of view and instead thinks for her. Individuals should understand that humor is directed at their irrationality, not at them. By using humor and creative approaches, such as stories and metaphors, the therapist can maintain a relationship in which the client is open to change and not argumentative. Therapists’ self-disclosure about how they themselves have used the A-B-C method to deal with their own irrational beliefs can also be helpful. Increased familiarity with disputing the irrational beliefs of clients can lead to the development of new strategies.

E (effective): When clients have disputed their irrational beliefs, they are then in a position to develop an effective philosophy. This philosophy, following the A-B-C model, helps individuals develop rational thoughts to replace inappropriate irrational thoughts. This new effective philosophy can bring about more productive behaviours, minimize feelings of depression and self-hatred, and bring about satisfying and enjoyable feelings (Sharf, 2010).

Other Cognitive Approaches

Rational emotive behaviour therapists apply a number of cognitive techniques that help individuals develop new rational beliefs. Many of these are used as an adjunct to, and in support of, disputing techniques. Their variety illustrates the creativity of rational emotive behaviour therapists and invalidates a misunderstanding that some have had that rational emotive behaviour therapists employ only disputing techniques.

Coping self-statements

By developing coping statements, rational beliefs can be strengthened. For example, an individual who is afraid of public speaking may write down and repeat to himself several times a day statements such as “I want to speak flawlessly, but it is all right if I don’t,” “No one is killed for giving a poor speech,” and “I am an articulate person.” (Sharf, 2012)

Cost-benefit analysis

This method is particularly helpful for individuals who have addictions and/or low frustration tolerance. Individuals who are addicted to smoking may be asked to make lists of the advantages of stopping smoking and the disadvantages of continuing smoking. They are then instructed to think seriously about these advantages and disadvantages 10 or 20 times a day. This activity gives them good reasons for overcoming the addiction (Ellis, 2003).

Emotive Techniques

Like other strategies, emotive techniques are both used in the session and assigned as homework. Some techniques such as imagery and visualization can be viewed as cognitive, emotive, or behavioural. When the emphasis is on emotional aspects, imagery becomes an emotive method of treatment. Role playing also has cognitive, emotional, and behavioural components and is used to get at the strong consequences that accompany irrational beliefs. Ellis believes that strong or powerful approaches are necessary to change irrational beliefs. Examples include shame-attacking exercises, forceful self-statements, and forceful self-dialogue. All of these techniques are used with the full acceptance of the therapist. The therapist not only accepts clients but also tries to communicate this acceptance so that clients accept themselves (Sharf, 2012).

Imagery

Imagery is often used in REBT to help clients change their inappropriate feelings to appropriate ones. For example, a man may vividly imagine that, if he is rejected by a woman he wishes to date, he will be terribly depressed afterward, be unable to think about anything else, and be very angry at himself. The therapist then would have him keep the same negative image and work on feeling the healthy emotions—disappointment and regret about the woman’s wish not to go out with him—without feeling depressed and angry at himself. Imagining asking the woman for a date, being turned down, and working on experiencing healthy rather than unhealthy negative emotions can help reduce depression and feelings of inadequacy. Preferably, such techniques should be practiced once a day for several weeks (Dryden & Ellis, 2003).

Role playing

Rehearsing certain behaviours to elicit client feelings often can bring out emotions the client was not previously aware of. For example, by role playing a situation in which a woman asks a man for a date, the woman can be aware of strong fears she did not know she had. Repeated role playing of the situation gives the individual a chance to feel better about her social skills and change inappropriate emotional self-statements (Ellis, 2003).

Shame-attacking exercises

The purpose of these exercises is to help clients feel unashamed when others may disapprove of them. Although the exercise can be practiced in a therapy session, it is done outside therapy. Examples include minor infractions of social conventions, such as talking loudly to a store clerk or engaging strangers in conversations. Asking silly questions to receptionists or teachers is another example. Such exercises are continued until one stops feeling sorry and disappointed about others' disapproval and ceases putting oneself down and feeling ashamed. Such exercises must be legal and not harmful for others. Inappropriate examples would be calling a 911 emergency number and leaving a false message or directing traffic in the middle of a street while playing the role of a police officer (Sharf, 2012).

Forceful self-statements

Statements that combat "musturbating" beliefs in a strong and forceful manner can be helpful in replacing irrational beliefs with rational beliefs. If a client has told himself that it is awful and terrible to get a C on an examination, this self-statement can be replaced by a forceful and more suitable statement such as "I want to get an A, but I don't have to!" Ellis often uses obscenities as a way of providing more force to a statement (Dryden & Ellis, 2003).

Forceful self-dialogue

In addition to single self-statements, a dialogue with oneself, somewhat similar to the Socratic dialogue, can be quite helpful. Arguing strongly and vigorously against an irrational belief has an advantage over therapist-client dialogue in that all of the material comes from the client. Taping such dialogues, listening to them over and over again, and letting listeners determine if one's disputing is really powerful can help clients impress themselves with their own power (Ellis, 1986c; Ellis, Gordon, Neenan, & Palmer, 1997 in Sharf, 2012).

Behavioural Methods

Rational emotive behaviour therapists make use of a wide variety of behavioural therapeutic approaches. These would include systematic desensitization, relaxation techniques, modeling, operant conditioning, and principles of self-management. Most behavioural techniques are carried out as homework. REBT has developed some new behavioural techniques in recent years (Ellis, 2003). Two behavioural methods frequently used by rational emotive behaviour therapists are activity, reinforcements and penalties, and skill training (Ellis, 1985, 1986c; Ellis & Dryden, 1997 in Sharf, 2012).

Reinforcements and penalties

When people accomplish a task, it is useful for them to reward themselves. For example, a shy person who has an extended conversation with three sales clerks may reward himself by reading a favorite magazine. Individuals who fail to attempt a task may penalize themselves. Ellis (2008) gives the example of burning a \$100 bill. Such a self-penalty can quickly encourage clients to complete agreed-upon assignments.

Skill training

Workshops and groups often teach important social skills. For example, assertiveness training workshops can be helpful for those who are shy and find it difficult to have their needs met by other people (Ellis, 1987). Workshops on communication skills, job-interviewing skills, and other social and work-related skills can supplement individual REBT. Although these techniques are divided into cognitive, emotive, and behavioral techniques, in actual practice some techniques fall into two or three of those categories. For example, Ellis (1987) made frequent use of humor in his application of a variety of methods and asks patients to learn songs he had written that challenge irrational beliefs in a whimsical, nonthreatening way. Decisions as to which techniques to employ come with experience in listening to clients discuss their irrational beliefs. Often the techniques previously described follow disputational techniques. As therapists evaluate how well clients handle various assignments and suggestions, they then revise and reassign other techniques or methods. As therapy progresses, clients often develop insight into their problems.

Conclusion

Rational emotive behaviour therapy asserts that it is not only events themselves that disturb people but also their beliefs about the events. This view leads to an approach to psychotherapy that stresses cognitive aspects of personality theory and therapeutic intervention yet also makes use of emotive and behavioural components. The philosophical assumptions are humanistic, hedonistic, and rational (self-helping and society helping). The focus is on individuals and their potential to overcome irrational (self-defeating) beliefs and to be responsible for their own lives. *Rationality* does not refer to an absence of emotion; rather, it refers to individuals' ability to use reason to guide their lives and to diminish the impact of irrational (dysfunctional) beliefs on their lives. *Responsible hedonism* refers to the concept of individuals seeking happiness over the long term, in contrast to short-term hedonism, which, in the case of alcoholism, for example, can lead to long-term difficulties. The notable contribution that Ellis has made to the treatment of sexual problems as well as his commitment to sex education through his writings is an example of his emphasis on increasing human happiness. Rational emotive behaviour therapy applies cognitive, emotive, and behavioural approaches to changing irrational beliefs. A major method for working with irrational beliefs is disputing, which involves detecting, discriminating, and debating irrational beliefs. The stronger emphasis on understanding the A-B-Cs of the development of one's irrational beliefs distinguishes REBT from other cognitive and behavioural therapies. However, REBT also uses other cognitive strategies, such as repeated constructive statements about oneself, audiotapes, and psycho-educational materials. Methods

that employ imagery along with emotions, exercises that attack beliefs that are shameful, and forceful self-dialogue are some of the emotive methods REBT uses. Behavioural methods include homework outside the session, skill training, and reinforcement of desired behavior. Rational emotive behavior therapists make use of a large number of techniques, primarily from other cognitive and behavioural therapies, as well as creative ones that they devise on their own, to help clients deal with strongly entrenched irrational beliefs.

Rational emotive behaviour therapists are tolerant of their clients and fully accept them. It is their behaviour that they dispute by challenging, confronting, and convincing the clients to practice activities in and out of therapy that will lead to constructive changes in thinking, feeling, and behaving. An active therapy, REBT includes insights about irrational beliefs and about becoming aware of how individuals harm themselves through absolutist beliefs and then uses these insights to make constructive changes in their lives.

Recommendations

It was recommended that seminars and workshops should constantly be organized for guidance and counselling officers/teachers to improve on their knowledge and skills on effective application of REBT techniques within and outside school setting.

Implications for Guidance and Counselling

Individual who develop irrational thought and beliefs about certain situations of life, action or event will certainly be experience emotional disturbance or psychological problems, such individual will not be able to adapt properly to their environment, while individual who develop rational thought and beliefs about certain situations of life, action or event will certainly be free from emotional disturbance or psychological problems and they will be able to adapt properly to their environment

Rational emotive behaviour therapy is the psychotherapeutic approaches which propose that unrealistic and irrational belief is the root causes of emotional disturbance or psychological problems of the clients. Therefore, REBT Therapists help to change the client irrational ideas, believes or negative thinking process to make them function effective and lives their normal life, these are some of the irrational ideas that were change to rational ideas: It is essential that a person beloved and approved by virtually everyone in the community. This is irrational because it is not an obtainable goal; one cannot have sincere love and approval almost all the time from all the people. A person must be perfectly competent, adequate and achieving to be considered worthwhile. To strive compulsively for this may result in psychosomatic illness, a sense of inferiority and a constant sense of fears of failure.

Some people are bad, wicked or villainous and therefore should be blamed and punished. This idea is irrational because there is no absolute standard of right or wrong and very little free will. It is terrible, catastrophe when thing are not as a person want them to be. This is irrational because thing may not always go the way you would like them to go. Unhappiness is caused by outside circumstances and a person has no control over it. This is irrational because unhappiness

comes largely from within, while the individual may be irritated by the external events, the individual's reactions can be changed by his or her definition and verbalization of these events

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